

Local Wisdom Based Religious Counseling to Reduce Student Bullying Behavior

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is related to religion counseling based on local wisdom in reducing student bullying behavior. Religion and local wisdom are important elements that have the potential to be implemented in counseling. Religious values and local wisdom are expected to increase the effectiveness of the counseling process. Religious values and local wisdom can be elements that support the client's acceptance of counseling interventions, so that the counseling process will be meaningful for the client. According to Rangks (2016), counseling with religious values combined with local wisdom has proven effective when implemented to overcome problems experienced by individuals. This study uses research and development (R&D). The development model used is the ADDIE Model (analyze, design, development, implementation, evaluation). The development results were validated by two counseling experts to obtain a feasibility test (validation) and reliability of the local wisdom-based religious counseling model. Next, a limited trial was conducted through an experiment with 10 (ten) students who were perpetrators of bullying. The instruments used were an expert validation sheet, a questionnaire about bullying behavior, and a questionnaire of students' responses to the local wisdom-based religious counseling they received. Data were analyzed using qualitative and quantitative descriptive analysis techniques. The results of the validation test by two (2) counseling experts were categorized as good (75%). Notes and suggestions for improvement included emphasizing the religious and local wisdom aspects more and telling more folktales related to friendship. Based on input and comments from these two counseling experts, the local wisdom-based religious counseling model underwent revision stage I. The implementation stage will end with an evaluation, namely revision stage II. Based on the experimental test data on students who were bullies, a reduction in bullying behavior was obtained with a difference in pretest and posttest scores of 52%. Then tested using the Wilcoxon test, a significant value of 0.005 was obtained, which is smaller than 0.05, meaning that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores. Students' responses to the local wisdom-based religious counseling they participated in were generally categorized as feeling happy, interesting, clear, and easy to understand. Overall, it can be concluded that the local wisdom-based religious counseling model developed is able to reduce student bullying behavior.

Keywords: Religious counseling; local wisdom; reducing bullying behavior

I. Introduction

As a nation rich in religious and cultural values, Indonesia should also strengthen various aspects of its distinctive Indonesian character. For comparison, religious and cultural humility, as part of a counselor's orientation, can help facilitate strong working alliances with clients of different religions and cultures (DeBlaere et al., 2019). The proposed intervention strategy focuses on developing individual identity for more effective decision-making and authentic living.

Multicultural competence is essential for counselors, which is essential for providing counseling services (Greene, 2018). Consideration of ethical conflicts and religious and cultural values is crucial for developing locally-based religious counseling (Delpechitre & Baker, 2017). A counselor must have multicultural competence in providing services to clients to reduce resistance in efforts to change the client's attitudes, ways of thinking and behavior (Sue & Sue, 2016).

In the context of Indonesia, with its highly diverse society, the most rational choice is to develop religious counseling based on local wisdom, incorporating religious and cultural values, especially those rich in values, as a response to these challenges. Many counseling experts state that no matter how strong a counselor's counseling skills are, they will be ineffective if religious and cultural empathy is not present in the counseling process.

Religion and local wisdom are important elements that have the potential to be implemented in counseling. Religious values and local wisdom are expected to increase the effectiveness of the counseling process. Religious values and local wisdom can be elements that support the client's acceptance of the counseling intervention, thereby making the counseling process meaningful for the client. According to Rangks (2016), counseling with religious values combined with local wisdom has proven effective in addressing the problems experienced by individuals. One of the Indigenous counseling programs that prioritizes optimizing local wisdom among Indonesian society, which has a variety of religions, cultures and ethnicities.

Local wisdom is a community culture created by ancestors and passed down to their descendants, serving as a means of controlling societal behavior. Values considered a means of social control are also considered religious values that serve as guidelines for human life. Meanwhile, values that align with religious values and local wisdom are perceived by society as individuals who fail to appreciate these values. With social change in society, local wisdom has been nearly forgotten by today's society and has been largely forgotten by history.

Religious values and local wisdom also encompass noble values that every citizen should possess, such as tolerance, empathy, selfless mutual assistance, good manners (politeness in speech and behavior), the ability to yield, and the ability to adapt to situations and conditions. These are positive attitudes that every human being should possess to prepare them for life in a society with diverse religions and cultures (Maulana, 2014). These values are sources of values that have long been held by society but are sometimes forgotten in the counseling process.

Based on the discussion above, it is clear that religious elements and local wisdom are important to consider in order to increase the effectiveness of the counseling process itself. Religious counseling based on local wisdom can utilize local religious and cultural values appropriate to the location where the counselor and client reside. Counselors need to be aware of the importance of integrating religious values and local wisdom in the counseling process. Creativity is also required, because without it, the integration of religious values and local wisdom in counseling will not be realized.

This requires innovative thinking from a counselor to become a solution-oriented individual who can help clients develop solutions to avoid or overcome the problems that bind them. The challenges above are clearly demonstrated by the various problems that arise among students. These problems arise as a result of students' instability in managing their emotions, one of which is bullying behavior.

Bullying behavior is an act of students who seemingly claim to be the best person they can be compared to other students, leading them to willingly harm others, either intentionally or unintentionally. Bullying is a form of anarchic behavior perpetrated by students, often characterized by groups of students seeking to injure or incapacitate their opponents through violence using sharp objects such as knives, arrows, and other objects. In fact, many deaths have occurred due to this type of behavior.

One of the main factors contributing to bullying behavior is the inability to think rationally when faced with certain situations. This condition makes it difficult for students to control their emotions, leading to harming others, both verbally and non-verbally. One effort counselors make to address this bullying problem is through the implementation of religious counseling based on local wisdom. This religious counseling process, based on local wisdom, encourages students to think critically, thus avoiding the idea of harming others, whether intentionally or unintentionally. Based on the description above, the problem can be formulated, namely "can religious counseling based on local wisdom reduce students' bullying behavior?"

II. Research methods

The research method used refers to the ADDIE model (analyze, design, development, implementation, evaluation). The indicators for each stage can be described as follows:

Stages and indicators of the ADDIE model steps

No.	Stages	<i>Indicator</i>
1	Needs analysis & problem definition	Theoretical study of research problems that are related to actual information that occurs in the field, literature review, FGD with experts tenpliersribullying behavior and religious counseling based on local wisdom.
2	Design	Producing a prototype in the form of a book and counseling guide based on religious values and local wisdom values in reducing bullying behavior. The design of a local wisdom-based religious counseling model includes the objectives of local wisdom-based religious counseling, task analysis, and assessment criteria in accordance with the objectives of local wisdom-based religious counseling, which is expected to receive input from the Focus Group Discussion (FGD) with experts on bullying behavior.a model of religious counseling based on local wisdom designed in the form of a guidebook containing: Chapter I: Introduction consists of: rationale, objectives, user targets, roles of counselor and counselee; Chapter II: Theoretical study consists of: A. Bullying Behavior: 1) concept of bullying behavior, 2) forms of bullying behavior.ribullying behavior, 3) dimensions of bullying behavior, 4) factsfactors of bullying behavior, B. Religious counseling, and C. Religious counseling

		based on local wisdom; Chapter III: Counseling Process Guide, consisting of: Instructions General Instructions, Special Instructions, Counseling Sessions, and SkenaRio Religious counseling based on local wisdom
3	Development	The counseling developed includes the following 6 stages: (1) rational counseling model; (2) exploring the root causes of bullying behavior; (3) pheno-reflection- (4) explain bullying behavior from various perspectives; (5) teach people to look for alternative solutions bullying behavior; (5) looking for different forms of bullying behavior and avoiding langand (6) evaluation and follow-up of thoughts, feelings, and behavior.
4	Implementation	The religious counseling based on local wisdom that has been produced is then tested by experts, namely 2 counseling experts and 2 cultural experts, so that no validity and validity the path can be measured and tested.
5	Evaluation	Carried out on (ten) students who were bullying.

The working mechanism of local wisdom-based religious counseling is a form of training conducted by counselors for clients. This training is conducted over six sessions, but can also be conducted outside of counseling sessions. This allows clients to internalize ways of thinking that can erode their desire to harm others, both verbally and nonverbally. This mindset can encourage students to live their lives according to their own desires and choices, as assessed by themselves, so that students' lives can grow better and more constructively (Hill, 2007).

The stages of this local wisdom-based religious counseling will be tested by two counseling experts. The experimental subjects will be 10 students who have been bullied. The data collected include validation data from the two counseling experts, data from the bullying behavior questionnaire, and student responses to the local wisdom-based religious counseling services they have received. Data analysis techniques used are qualitative and descriptive quantitative.

2.1 Research result

a. Analysis Stage

The analysis phase is where researchers identify problems related to bullying behavior among students who have been served by guidance and counseling (BK) teachers. Activities conducted at this stage include student observations and interviews with guidance and counseling teachers. The results of student observations and interviews with guidance and counseling teachers revealed several findings, including:

1. There are 35 students in one class.
2. Of these 35 students, 10 exhibit bullying behavior toward other students, both verbally and nonverbally.
3. Bullying behavior by students tends to be considered normal.

Based on the results of the problem analysis, several issues were identified: students engage in arbitrary bullying (both verbally and nonverbally) toward other students, causing the victims to feel uneasy and want the bullying to stop happening again at school.

Based on interviews with guidance and counseling teachers, to address this bullying problem, a counseling model is needed that can reduce bullying behavior. With this counseling

model, it is hoped that students will no longer bully other students and will create a peaceful and calm atmosphere among students at school. Therefore, efforts are needed to develop counseling models, one of which is a religious counseling model based on local wisdom to reduce student bullying behavior.

b. Design Stage

This stage is the design process for a local wisdom-based religious counseling model. To design this counseling model, a design sketch is needed to facilitate the local wisdom-based religious counseling process. This sketch is incorporated into a working mechanism for the counseling. The working mechanism sketch developed in this research is as follows:

The product design is a guideline for a counseling model combining religion and local wisdom to facilitate guidance and counseling teachers in providing counseling to students who bully. This counseling model is the result of initial development, which will then be tested for validation (feasibility) and reliability. The following is an overview of the results of this initial product development, a guideline for a religious counseling model based on local wisdom, containing three chapters:

1. Chapter I: Introduction, consisting of: rationale, objectives, target users, roles of counselors and clients;
2. Chapter II: Theoretical Review, consisting of: A. Bullying Behavior: 1) concept of bullying behavior, 2) forms of bullying behavior, 3) dimensions of bullying behavior, 4) factors influencing bullying behavior; B. Religious counseling; and C. Counseling based on local wisdom;
- 3 Chapter III: Counseling Process Guide, consisting of: General Instructions, Special Instructions, Counseling Sessions, and Local Wisdom-based Religious Counseling Scenarios.

c. Development

The development stages of a local wisdom-based religious counseling model to reduce bullying behavior include the following 6 stages: (1) rationale for local wisdom-based religious counseling; (2) exploring the root causes of bullying behavior; (3) reflection on the phenomenon of bullying behavior from various perspectives; (4) teaching and seeking alternatives to bullying behavior; (5) seeking different forms of bullying behavior and trying to eliminate them; and (6) evaluation and follow-up of thoughts, feelings, and behavior. The following describes the

implementation of the 6 general process stages of the local wisdom-based religious counseling model to reduce student bullying behavior as follows:

Meeting 1: The rationale for a local wisdom-based religious counseling model is to

coup:

1. The counselor greets and thanks the client for coming to meet the counselor and greets them enthusiastically and enthusiastically and prays.
2. Build good relationships with students by asking how they are, and then providing ice breaking.
3. Ask students about their readiness to participate in counseling.
4. The counselor explains the purpose and objectives of inviting the client to the counseling session.
5. The counselor asks the client to write a willingness sheet. follow local wisdom-based religious counseling services.
6. The counselor and client agree on the rules during the counseling session.
7. The counselor identifies the location of the problems experienced by the client.
8. The counselor encourages the client to conclude the results of the first counseling meeting and the counselor provides feedback.
9. The counselor encourages the client to fill out the counseling reflection journal at meeting I.
10. The counselor closes the first counseling meeting.

Meeting 2: Digging into the root of the problem of bullying

1. The counselor greets and thanks the client for coming to meet the counselor and greets them enthusiastically and enthusiastically and prays.
2. Build good relationships with students by asking how they are, and then providing ice breaking.
3. Ask students about their readiness to participate in counseling.
4. The counselor explains the purpose and objectives of inviting the client to the counseling session.
5. The counselor encourages the client to reflect on the first counseling session
6. The counselor explains the outline of the counseling session two.
7. The counselor asks for clarity regarding the client's problems and contributing factors.- chapter.
8. The counselor encourages the client to conclude the second counseling meeting.
9. The counselor asks the client to fill out a self-reflection journal sheet.
10. The counselor makes an agreement to meet with the client at the 3rd meeting and closes the counseling meeting.

Meeting 3: Meeting 3: Reflection on the phenomenon of bullying behavior from various perspectives.

1. The counselor greets and thanks the client for coming to meet the counselor and greets them enthusiastically and enthusiastically and prays.
2. Build good relationships with students by asking how they are, and then providing ice breaking.
3. Ask students about their readiness to participate in counseling.
4. The counselor explains the purpose and objectives of inviting the client to the counseling session.
5. The counselor encourages the client to reflect on the counseling session two.
6. The counselor explains the outline of the counseling session three.

7. The counselor shows an example of an event (folk story) that has the potential to give rise to bullying behavior.
8. The counselor invites students to discuss folk tales that are read from various perspectives, including the client's instincts if they are in the situation in the folk tale.
9. The counselor concludes the counseling meeting and provides feedback.
10. The counselor asks the client to fill out a self-reflection journal.
11. The counselor makes an agreement to meet with the client at the four se and session closes the counseling session.
- 12.

Meeting 4: Teaching and finding alternatives to bullying behavior

1. The counselor greets and thanks the client for coming to meet the counselor and greets them enthusiastically and enthusiastically and prays.
2. Build good relationships with students by asking how they are, and then providing ice breaking.
3. Ask students about their readiness to participate in counseling.
4. The counselor explains the purpose and objectives of inviting the client to the counseling session.
5. The counselor asks the client about their readiness for the counseling session.
6. The counselor encourages the client to reflect on the counseling session three.
7. The counselor explains the description of the counseling session four.
8. The counselor shows the client's instinct to think about the folktales discussed at session three.
9. The counselor encourages the client to seek thoughts about brotherhood in the case situation which is exemplified as resistance to the client's destructive thought instincts.
10. The counselor concludes the counseling meeting and provides feedback.
11. The counselor asks the client to write a self-reflection journal.
12. The counselor ends the counseling activities at session four.

Meeting 5: Look for different forms of bullying behavior and try to eliminate them.

1. The counselor greets and thanks the client for coming to meet the counselor and greets them enthusiastically and enthusiastically and prays.
2. Build good relationships with students by asking how they are, and then providing ice breaking.
3. Ask students about their readiness to participate in counseling.
4. The counselor explains the purpose and objectives of inviting the client to the counseling session.
5. The counselor asks about the client's readiness for the five counseling session.
6. The counselor encourages the client to reflect on the counseling session four.
7. The counselor explains the outline of the counseling session five.
8. The counselor confirms the clarity of the problem and the factors that cause the client to engage in bullying behavior.
9. The counselor encourages the client to look for different forms of the client's destructive thoughts, namely forms of sibling thoughts regarding the problem situation being experienced.
10. The counselor encourages the client to conclude session five.
11. The counselor asks the client to write a self-reflection journal.
12. The counselor ends the counseling activity at session five.

Meeting 6: Evaluation and follow-up

1. The counselor greets and thanks the client for coming to meet the counselor and greets them enthusiastically and enthusiastically and prays.
2. Build good relationships with students by asking how they are, and then providing ice breaking.
3. Ask students about their readiness to participate in counseling.
4. The counselor explains the purpose and objectives of inviting the client to the counseling session.
5. The counselor asks the client about their readiness in the 6th counseling session.
6. The counselor encourages the client to reflect on the five counseling session
7. The counselor explains the description of religious counseling at session six.
8. The counselor identifies the client's efforts to reduce bullying behavior and its obstacles.
9. The counselor encourages the client to explain possible action plans that will be taken if these obstacles arise.
10. The counselor provides feedback and concludes the counseling activities at session six.
11. The counselor asks the client to fill out a self-reflection journal sheet.
12. The counselor closes the six counseling session.

d. Implementation

After the local wisdom-based religious counseling model was developed, it was implemented through feasibility testing (validation). Validation of the developed counseling model was conducted by two counseling experts. This validation is illustrated in the following table:

No	Aspect	Indicator	reviewer	
			1	2
1	suitability of counseling content	Counseling coverage with bullying behavior	1	2
		The relationship between religious counseling and local wisdom base with bullying behavior	1	1
		The relevance of the objectives of religious counseling based on local wisdom to reduce bullying behavior	2	2
		The suitability of local wisdom-based religious counseling service materials to reduce bullying behavior	1	2
2	material accuracy	Truth and accuracy of concepts	2	2
		The truth and accuracy of the theory	1	2
3	presentation components	Quality of counseling services provided	1	1
		Encourage students to understand the content of the service	1	1
		Stimulate student participation.	1	1
		Systematics/sequence/logical flow	1	2
		Easy for students to understand	1	2
4	language aspects	The language used is easy for students to understand	1	1
		Not ambiguous	1	1
5	service suitability	The suitability of counseling services to reduce bullying behavior.	1	2
		Suitability of counseling services for	1	1

		individuals/groups		
		The effectiveness of the counseling services used	1	2
		Effective and efficient in developing counseling models	1	2
		Creativity and ideas	1	2
		Communicative (on target and acceptable to the target's wishes)	2	2
	quality of service	. Usability (easy to use and simple to operate)	1	2
		. Reusable (some/all of this model can be reused for the development of other counseling services)	1	1
	comments and suggestions	. Comment		
		. Suggestion		
Total			24	34

The conclusion from the validation results of the two counseling experts mentioned above, it can be concluded that both counseling experts are of the view that local wisdom-based religious counseling can be categorized as good (75%). One expert stated that 18 indicators were very good and 3 indicators were good, and another counseling expert stated that 8 indicators were very good and 13 indicators were good. In addition, comments and suggestions for improvement were to emphasize religious values and local wisdom more and to tell more folk tales related to friendship. Furthermore, based on input and comments from these two counseling experts, the local wisdom-based religious counseling model was revised in phase I.

e. Evaluation Stage

The implementation phase will end with an evaluation, namely a second phase revision conducted based on data from a limited trial through an experiment with students who were bullies. This limited trial was conducted with 10 students who were bullies as an implementation of the local wisdom-based religious counseling model that had been revised in phase I, which was a revision by two counseling experts. This trial was conducted in an effort to determine and understand changes in bullying behavior after receiving local wisdom-based religious counseling services that students received. It began with a pre-test (bullying behavior questionnaire), followed by treatment (local wisdom-based religious counseling), and ended with a post-test (bullying behavior questionnaire). The results of the limited trial are as attached in the following table:

No	Aspect	Indicator	Answer		% Change
			Pretest	Posts	
1	Direct physical contact	hitting,	36	13	58
		pushing,	34	18	40
		biting,	36	16	50
		pulling hair,	36	17.	48
		kicking,	33	14	48
		locking in a room	33	13	50
		pinching,	36	16	50
		scratching	35	16	48
		blackmailing	36	12	60

		destroying	34	13	58
2	Direct verbal contact	threaten,	33	13	50
		humiliate,	33	13	50
		belittle	31	14	48
		annoy,	32	13	48
		call names	27	15	30
		insult/mock,			
		curse,	32	15	43
		spread gossip	34	15	48
			35	15	40
3	Direct non-verbal behaviour	to look scornfully,	39	15	60
		to stick out one's tongue,	37	17	50
			35	17	45
		to display a condescending facial expression,	34	16	45
		to mock/threaten			
4	Indirect nonverbal behaviour	to ignore	32	14	45
		to manipulate a friendship	32	13	48
		to deliberately exclude or ignore	34	13	53
		to send anonymous mail.	36	16	50
Total			885	383	52%

From the table above, it can be concluded that the change in bullying behavior reached a percentage change of 52 (fairly good). A Wilcoxon test then demonstrated a decrease in pretest to posttest scores, with a significance value of 0.005, which is less than 0.05, indicating a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores (analysis results are attached).

The pretest scores administered prior to the study showed a class average of 88.5. This indicates a high level of student bullying behavior. Furthermore, the average posttest score was 38.3 (low). This indicates a 52% reduction in student bullying behavior, as shown in the following figure:

Next, a questionnaire was distributed regarding students' responses to local wisdom-based religious counseling they received can be explained in the following table:

No.	Statement	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Interest in the appearance of guidance and counseling teachers in implementing local wisdom-based religious counseling services	yes									
2	Feel happy if the supervising teacher provides religious counseling based on local wisdom	yes									
3	Given the opportunity to ask questions if you encounter difficulties in understanding	yes									
	The teacher's response to the students' questions was quite interesting and engaging.	yes									
4	What do guidance and counseling teachers convey in counseling services?MA based on local wisdom can touch students' feelings	yes									
5	The material presented is easy to understand	yes									
6	Providing learning opportunities	yes									
7	Simple and charming	yes									
8	Quality and motivation	yes									

Evaluation of student responses, the results was categorized as they felt happy, interesting, clear and easy to understand.

III. Result and Discussion

Based on the presentation of this development research, the results obtained serve as the objectives of developing a local wisdom-based religious counseling model to reduce student bullying behavior. This development uses the ADDIE model, which consists of five stages: (1) Analysis; (2) Design; (3) Development; (4) Implementation; and (5) Evaluation.

The first stage is the analysis stage, which consists of two stages: a Needs Assessment, which analyzes the field conditions and students who engage in bullying behavior, which is the subject of discussion in developing the local wisdom-based religious counseling model.

The second stage is the design stage, which is the design stage for the local wisdom-based religious counseling model, which includes the following six stages: (1) rationale for the local wisdom-based religious counseling model; (2) exploring the root causes of bullying behavior; (3) reflecting on the phenomenon of bullying behavior from various perspectives; (4) teaching and seeking alternatives to bullying behavior; (5) identifying different forms of bullying behavior and eliminating them. and (6) evaluation and follow-up of thoughts, feelings, and behavior. The six stages above are outlined in a guide. The guide contains three chapters: Chapter I: Introduction, consisting of: rationale, objectives, target users, and the roles of counselors and clients; Chapter II: Theoretical Review, consisting of: A. Bullying Behavior: 1) the concept of bullying behavior, 2) forms of bullying behavior, 3) dimensions of bullying behavior, 4) factors of bullying behavior; B. Religious counseling, and C. Local wisdom-based religious counseling; Chapter III: Counseling Process Guide, consisting of: General Instructions, Specific Instructions, and Scenarios for local wisdom-based religious counseling.

The third stage is Development. This development stage is the stage of creating and developing a local wisdom-based religious counseling model. After the counseling model is developed, the fourth stage is implementation. At this stage, after the local wisdom-based religious counseling model is developed, its feasibility (validation) is tested. The feasibility test (validation) of the developed local wisdom-based religious counseling model was conducted by two counseling experts. The results of the feasibility test concluded that the model was considered feasible and good.

The fifth stage was evaluation. The development evaluation was conducted through a limited trial experiment with 10 students who engaged in bullying behavior. The evaluation provided data describing the quality of the counseling service, categorizing it as enjoyable, engaging, clear, and easy to understand.

Bullying remains a problem that remains unresolved. In fact, the forms of bullying are increasingly complex. Bullying is becoming easier for students to engage in because they lack the immediate concern of the direct impact of their bullying behavior. The concept of conventional aggressive behavior is based solely on behavior that directly harms others, either physically or non-physically. However, with the emergence of social aggression, this behavior is not limited to directly harming others, but also involves indirect harm. For example, ignoring someone they hate for a specific purpose.

Bullying behavior problems can be reduced by implementing a religious counseling model based on local wisdom. The goal of this local wisdom-based religious counseling model is to create awareness of individuals' thoughts and feelings so that these thought processes can suppress the urge to bully. They will seek alternative, more constructive behaviors when their bullying urges are high.

This religious counseling model combines local wisdom with the goal of increasing its effectiveness, particularly in reducing bullying behavior. Religious elements and local wisdom can support clients' acceptance of counseling interventions, making the counseling process meaningful for them. A local wisdom-based religious counseling model can utilize local religious and cultural values appropriate to the region where the counselor and client reside. Counselors need to be creative and aware of the importance of integrating local religious and cultural values into counseling.

IV. Conclusion

1. The local wisdom-based religious counseling model for reducing bullying behavior, developed using the ADDIE model, encompasses a multi-stage process including analysis, design, development, implementation, and evaluation.
2. Based on the results of a feasibility test (validation) of local wisdom-based religious counseling for reducing bullying behavior by two counseling experts, this counseling can be categorized as suitable (valid) for use.
3. Based on the results of a limited trial on 10 students who were bullies through an experiment, it was concluded that there was a change in bullying behavior reaching a percentage of 52 (fairly good). A Wilcoxon test revealed a decrease in pretest to posttest scores, with a significance value of 0.005, which is less than 0.05, indicating a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores.
4. The list of pretest scores administered prior to the study showed a class average score of 88.5. This score indicates that students' bullying behavior is classified as high. Furthermore, the average post-test score was 38.3 (categorized as low). There appears to be a 52% reduction in student bullying behavior.
5. Based on student responses, it can be concluded that the local wisdom-based religious counseling service they participated in was categorized as enjoyable, interesting, clear, and easy to understand.

Suggestion

1. For other researchers, it is hoped that they can address the shortcomings of the local wisdom-based religious counseling model that has not optimally facilitated students.
2. For other researchers, it is hoped that when developing a local wisdom-based counseling model to reduce bullying behavior, the model used should be self-developed to improve quality and ensure a user-friendly menu.
3. For other researchers, it is hoped that further research will be conducted to implement local wisdom-based religious counseling to measure the extent of changes in students' behaviors other than bullying, including violent, aggressive, negative behaviors, and others.

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